

THREE DIMENSIONAL FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF STRESSES AROUND A
PIN-LOADED HOLE IN A COMPOSITE LAMINATE

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results from a 3-dimensional finite element analysis and photoelasticity experiment of stresses around a pin-loaded hole in G/E composite laminates. The 3D-finite element analysis employs the program LXC-3D developed by author, it can be operated in micro-computer PC-XT or AT. The calculated results show good agreement with experimental date.

INTRODUCTION

Because of the widespread usage of fiber-reinforced composite materials in structures, there have been a number of studies to determine the stress distribution around a pin-loaded hole in composite laminates and to predict strengths of pin jointed composite laminates [1-8]. However, these studies were only twodimensional plane stress analysis based on Classical Lamination Theory, and can neither determine the interlaminar stress nor predict accurately the bearing strength since its failure mechanisms are three-dimensional.

In the present work, a 3-dimensional finite element model, named composite element [14], is adopted. Taking into account of that the pin elasticity causes little effect on stress distributions at the hole edge [6], the loaded hole boundary conditions are imposed by introducing radial displacement constraints at the contact surface.

In the experiment, the reflection photoelasticity is used to determine stresses around pin-loaded holes in composite laminates. this method is particularly useful for determining stresses on free(unloaded) surface of the prototype.

DESCRIPTION OF THE COMPOSITE ELEMENT

In the present paper, a 20-noded isoparametric composite element is chosen. Different from Classical Lamination Theory, for the composite element, the material properties are not taken as homogeneous within an element. They are taken discontinuous from layer to layer (of course, taken as continuous, homogeneous and anisotropic within a layer), and displacement within an element is still formulated as ordinary isoparametric elements.

Fig.1 shows the element containing n unidirectional layers. The element stiffness matrix can be given as follows:

$$K = \sum_{i=1}^n \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 B^T D_i B |J| A_i d\xi d\eta d\zeta$$

Fig. 1

where B is the element strain matrix and J is Jacobian transformation matrix.

$$A_i = (t_i - t_{i-1})/2$$

$D_i = T_i C T_i^T$ is the elastic properties matrix for the i th layer.

T_i is the usual transformation relating Cartesian strains to strains in the principal directions of the i th Layer, and C is elastic properties matrix in the principal directions of a layer.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND EXPERIMENT DATA

In the numerical procedure, a pin joint is treated as a frictionless rigid core inserted into a laminate with a hole of the same diameter as that of the pin. Figure 2 shows the laminate with a pin-loaded hole, coordinate axes, geometry and simple uniaxial loads. A G/E laminate $\{0_2/90_2/0\}_s$ is taken as a representative composite materials for the numerical calculations. Each unidirectional ply has a thickness of 0.6mm giving a 10-ply laminate 6 mm thick. Due to the symmetry of the laminate and the applied load, only 1/4 of the laminate is modeled, and the corresponding boundary conditions are imposed. Fig.3 shows the finite element mesh, only one composite element is used through the half-thickness of the laminate. The boundary conditions of the loaded hole are imposed by introducing radial displacement constraints at the nodes of the contact surface between the pin and the hole. In this study, the limit of the contact angle is given by $\theta = 72^\circ$ (only 9° increments being possible with the mesh adopted). This compares with 74° found by workers [6].

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4 In-plane stress distributions around the pin-loaded hole

Fig. 5 Variation of interlaminar shear stress σ_{z0} in each ply around the hole edge

Fig. 6 Variation of direct stress σ_z in each ply around the hole edge

Fig.4 shows the results of the in-plane stress distribution around a pin-loaded hole in the laminate by 3D-finite element analysis. The results of photoelastic experiment are also given in the figure. It is found that the results of 3D-analysis agree well with experimental data.

Fig.5 shows the distribution of interlaminar shear stress $\sigma_{z\theta}$ in plies. For all plies, the high value occurs around $\theta=30^\circ$ and $\theta=70^\circ$ with the maximum value of 15% nominal bearing stress σ_b ($\sigma_b=P/dt$) at $\theta=30^\circ$ in the outer 0° ply. The values of $\sigma_{z\theta}$ is very small at $\theta=0$ and $\theta=90^\circ$.

Fig.6 shows the distribution of the through-thickness stress σ_z around the hole edge in plies (that of ply 3 and 5 are not given since they are similar to ply 2 and 4, respectively). It is found that at $\theta=0^\circ$, σ_z is very small in the 0° ply but reaches its maximum tensile value $0.075\sigma_b$ in 90° plies. In all 0° plies the maximum tensile stress σ_z occurs around $\theta=90^\circ$ with the value about $0.07\sigma_b$.

There occurs the high tensile stress σ_z around the bearing region of the hole edge in the 90° ply. It may contribute to split of the matrix or to delamination between plies and reduce the bearing strength of laminates. This is consistent with the experimentally observed failure mode [16].

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the present analysis shows that the 3D-finite element model used here gives good agreement with experimental data. The 3D-analysis also suggest that the interlaminar stresses around a pin-loaded hole in a composite laminate are unnegligible. The strength analysis must include interlaminar stresses. The present results also show that it is convenient and feasible using radial displacement boundary conditions.